

THE CONCEPT AND FEATURES OF THE ENVIRONMENTAL POLICY OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the current environmental policy of the Republic of Uzbekistan, as well as the theoretical and legal basis of environmental policy based on the views of scientists. According to the end of the analysis, the existing problems in the field of environmental policy were analyzed and suggestions for their solution were developed.

Environmental policy is one of the main types of state policy implemented in the "society - nature" system.

The current state of the environment in the Republic of Uzbekistan requires a scientifically based environmental policy aimed at preserving the natural environment, rational use of natural resources and ensuring the environmental safety of the population.

In the context of the growing ecological crisis, the state and law face the most important tasks to prevent environmental danger. "Humanity's choice is to reduce the burden on nature caused by human activity to a sustainable level through reasonable policy, reasonable technology and reasonable organization, or wait until, as a result of changes in nature, the amount of energy, raw materials decreases and a completely unsuitable for living environment¹. Hence, the main task

of the state is to conduct a reasonable environmental policy based on the concentration and coordination of all means and forces of public life.

Before defining the concept, identifying the features and components of environmental policy, in our opinion, it is necessary to analyze such concepts as "politics", "state policy", "legal policy", because they are defining categories.

So what is "politics" anyway? The term "politics" comes from the Greek word politika, meaning state or public affairs. Politics is an activity in the sphere of relations between large social groups, parties, nations and states².

The prominent scientist and statesman Nizomulmulk, who lived in the 11th century, in his work "Siyosatnoma" considers "politics" as the ability to organize the management of the state and public affairs³. Khusain Koshifiy, a

¹ Медоуз Д.Х., Медоуз Д.Л., Рандерс Й., За пределами роста. М., 1994. С. 29.

² Краткий политический словарь. М., Политиздат, 1999. С. 178.

³ Низомулмулк. Сиёсатнома. Т., 1998. С. 121.

contemporary of Alisher Navoi, argued that politics regulates the state⁴. Aristotle defined politics as the art of government. Democritus considered this art to be the highest of all arts. In the nineteenth century, these ideas were developed by M. Weber, W. Humboldt and other scientists. Modern political scientists, relying on the thinkers of the past (J.J. Rousseau, T. Hobbes, J. Locke, S. L. Montesquieu, etc.), emphasize that politics is also the art of the possible, the art of compromise, the art of coordinating the desired and objectively achievable, the ability to reckon with reality. An effective, wise, realistic policy is the key to the prosperity and well-being of nations, the stability of society. The main thing in politics (its core, core) is state power, its conquest, retention and use. All major social forces, parties, movements usually strive for power, the implementation of their program requirements. Therefore, the theory of politics is to a large extent a theory of statehood. Everything else revolves around this rod. The state is the nucleus, the nerve center of all politics⁵.

It is well known that the state is the center of the political system of society. Politics means public activity aimed at the exercise or preservation of state power, a certain direction and methods of state activity within the country and in relations with foreign states⁶.

To solve the goals and objectives necessary for the sustainable development of society and nature, the implementation of an appropriate policy on a nationwide

scale is required. That is why the sustainable development of society depends on the reasonable conduct of state policy.

Politics as a complex category covers various aspects of public life. According to the areas of implementation of a particular goal and the corresponding tasks, the following types of state policy are distinguished: internal and external, economic, social, scientific and technical, demographic, national, cultural, environmental and others.

The environmental policy of the state is decisive in the system of varieties of state policy, because. it covers literally all aspects of social life, and the fate of other spheres of society to a large extent depends on its effective implementation.

Therefore, the key goal of our study is to determine the main directions and components of environmental policy, improve its legislative framework, as well as develop a social and legal mechanism for implementing this policy.

Before proceeding to the study of theoretical and legal issues of the main directions of the environmental policy of the state and the features of its implementation in the "society-nature" system, it is necessary, in our opinion, to give a scientific definition of the concept of "environmental policy".

There are several different approaches to the definition of this concept in the legal literature. Thus, the "Legal Encyclopedic Dictionary" defines environmental policy as a policy aimed at protecting and improving the environment, rational use and renewal of natural

⁴ Исломов З.М. Хаёт ва конун. 2002, № 5. С. 10.

⁵ Матузов Н.И., Малько А.В. Теория государства и права. М.: «Юристъ», 2001. С. 491.

⁶ Исламов З.М. Общество. Государство. Право. Т. 2001. С. 30.

resources, ensuring normal human life and environmental safety⁷.

In the dictionary-reference book N.F. Reimers, environmental policy is divided into global and state. Ecopolitics on a global scale is the conduct of international legal, political and foreign economic actions, taking into account environmental restrictions in socio-economic development, the reserves of natural resources available in the world, and their distribution between countries. State ecopolitics is a socio-economic policy, including international, built on an understanding of the gains and disadvantages associated with the ecological state of the country's territory and water area and the natural resources available within them⁸.

The most extensive interpretation of this concept is given by Y.Shadimetov. In his opinion, environmental policy should be understood as such a direction of the state's activity, which allows optimally and effectively to regulate relationships in the "society - nature" system⁹.

According to GZ Abdullayeva, the environmental policy of the state is a process, the purpose of which is to develop and implement solutions to environmental problems. These decisions, in essence, are the state policy in the field of ecology¹⁰.

Environmental policy is also defined today as "the activity of subjects (individual, group, party, state, international governmental and non-

governmental organizations, etc.) that use the means, forms and methods of political power in order to protect and improve the natural environment, rational use and renewal of natural resources, preservation and development of society, the individual and human civilization as a whole"¹¹. This definition, on the one hand, covers the activities of the subjects of environmental policy, on the other hand, the spheres of environmental protection.

The well-known French political scientist, leader of the French Green Party Antoine Vechter, considering ecology through the prism of political activity, argues that "politics is the art of making choices, bringing social contradictions to the discussions that precede the decision, correctly correlating values in the process of managing society, translating into area specific social concept. As the practice of economic logic, which it serves, as the assertion of new values, which necessarily correspond to certain forms of social organization and social relations, ecology, of course, is politics¹².

According to MNEPU scientists, environmental policy in practice is a policy of safety, reducing environmental risk. Ecopolitics is called upon to be precisely politics, the art of the possible, that is, to maintain an optimal balance between various interests, preferences, scientifically based decisions fixed in environmental legal norms¹³.

⁷ Экология. Юридический энциклопедический словарь. М.: Норма, 2000. С.290.

⁸ Реймерс Н.Ф. Природопользование. Словарь-справочник. М.: Мысль, 1990. С. 598-599.

⁹ Шадиметов Ю. Введение в социозэкологию. Ташкент: Укитувчи, 1993. С. 232.

¹⁰ Абдуллаева Г. Экологическая политика Республики Узбекистан в условиях поэтапной интеграции в мировое сообщество. Автореф.дисс. на соиск.учен.ст. канд. полит.н. Т. 2001.

¹¹ Зарубежная политология. Словарь-справочник. М. Независимый открытый университет. 1998. С.89.

¹² Waechter A. Dessine – moi la planete. P: Albin Michel, 1990. p. 236.

¹³ Коваленко В.И., Костин А.И., Моисеев Н.Н., Степанов С.А. Экологическая безопасность и концепция эколога-политологического

A group of scientists from Ukraine similarly considers ecopolitics as a policy of environmental security, that is, a type of development of society (as a subject of an ecosystem) that is implemented in the interests of both the subject and the object (environment) of the ecosystem, while unconditionally observing the primacy of safety¹⁴.

In these definitions, ecopolitics is interpreted as a public attitude aimed at ensuring environmental safety. In our opinion, such a definition is narrow, since Ensuring environmental safety as a sphere of activity of the state is only one of the main directions of environmental policy.

It should be noted that a unique and most comprehensive definition of ecopolitics is given by E.N.Lisitsin. He considers environmental policy as a direction of "the functioning of the political system as a whole and its individual components, the activities of the state and its bodies, which allow the most optimal and effective regulation of complex socio-economic relationships in the "nature - society" system¹⁵.

In this definition, E.N. Lisitsin focuses on the areas of activity of state bodies focused on solving environmental issues in the system of socio-economic parameters.

A similar position is held by Y.Shadimetov, who believes that "environmental policy can be defined as a kind of socio-economic policy aimed at

choosing and implementing a certain type of interrelationships between society and nature, based on the appropriate type of production, forms of socio-economic life of society and personal factor"¹⁶.

In the concept of "environmental policy", along with the environmental functions of the state, some scientists also include a number of other areas and aspects, in particular: biosocial, environmental, demographic, socio-cultural, in which the human dimension of progress, public morality, value approaches are expressed¹⁷.

Having analyzed the statements of various scientists regarding the definition of the concept of "environmental policy", we believe that this concept can be formulated as follows:

Environmental policy is a set of socio-political, socio-economic, cultural, educational, organizational and legal measures of subjects (individual, group, party, state, etc.) aimed at environmental protection, rational use of natural resources and ensuring environmental safety of the population.

In our opinion, this definition differs in that, firstly, it unites all spheres of public life; secondly, it specifies the actors of environmental policy, including international non-governmental organizations, and thereby emphasizes the responsibility of each person and humanity as a whole for the state of the environment; thirdly, the direction of the activities of environmental policy subjects is clearly specified.

It is necessary to emphasize the fact that when it comes to environmental

образования в России. Вестник Московского университета, 1993. С. 8.

¹⁴ Качинский А.Б., Чердниченко В.П. Экологическая политика и безопасность Украинского государства. Восточная Европа политический и социокультурный выбор. Материалы конференции. Минск, 1994. С. 103.

¹⁵ Лисицин Е.Н. Экологическая политика буржуазных стран: право и управление. М., ИНИОН АН СССР, 1985. С. 35.

¹⁶ Шадиметов Ю. Введение в социоэкологию: Учебник. Т. 1, Т.: Укитувчи, 1992. С. 223.

¹⁷ Политологический словарь. Т.1, М., 1994. С. 144.

policy, it mainly refers to the activities of the state, public administration bodies, rather than the environmental policy of an individual, a social group, a political party or public organizations. This is explained by the fact that, first of all, the state is the core of the political system of society, the main actor, the main subject in the interaction of the system "society - nature". Further, it is the state through the state authorities and management that coordinates the activities of other subjects of environmental policy. And most importantly, the state has the means, including coercion, to implement its political attitudes.

That is why the main purpose of our dissertation work is to study the scientific and theoretical foundations, goals, objectives and legal support of priority areas of environmental policy of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The environmental policy of each independent State, including the Republic of Uzbekistan, is implemented at the international and national level.

In recent decades, environmental policy has taken one of the first places among the global problems of mankind, such as the threat of a thermonuclear war and an arms race, a demographic explosion, and food problems. These problems are truly planetary in nature both in terms of the coverage of the territory and in terms of the efforts needed to solve them, and therefore require the close attention of all political actors without exception, first of all, heads of State and Government. Thus, we are talking about the development of a deeply thought-out and purposeful policy that allows us to effectively solve the problems of human civilization within the framework of international cooperation.

Uzbekistan, as a full-fledged subject of the international community, pursues a national environmental policy based on international legal norms, but at the same time takes into account the economic, social, climatic and other features of our country.

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